

Clone city: modernism, landscape and the crisis of the European conurbation

The 'old' countries of Europe have, in the past decade or so, fallen into a disorientating process of spatial and social fragmentation, with everything increasingly dissolving into a mosaic of islands of specialised uses. This process is already well established in lower density urban areas in America and elsewhere, but it takes a different form in Europe. Here the mosaic is made up of 'inner' areas, dominated by imagery of the 'traditional dense city' and 'mixed use community', and 'outer' areas dominated by an anarchic proliferation of mass produced low density environments and privatised transport infrastructure. Through the pervasiveness of this loosely flexible formula, once highly variegated places across the whole continent are subtly homogenised into one uniform 'Clone City', with its standardised urban villages, heritage areas and business parks. The result is a loss of 'identity', and a growing socio-spatial division and injustice. These images of Clone City in Scotland could equally apply to this recent text about the state of historic Italian cities, which argued that 'shopping malls, discotheques, row houses, little single-family villas, warehouses and small industries, car parks and multi-screen cinemas constitute the distinguishing features of an unprecedented territory, that has until now remained disconcertingly invisible to traditional Italian architectural culture'.

What is the role of the Modern heritage in all this? Well once, as we know, to speak of a 'Modern heritage' would have seemed an oxymoron, as the two words were actually polarised against each other

- in a way typical of the violent, disciplined modernity of the late 19th and early/mid 20th centuries. On the one hand, there was the aggressive historical materialism of the 'high' Modern Movement, demonstrating its confident drive for social Progress spatially in an open-ended concept of landscape, which embraced the design not just of individual buildings but also, through 'planning', of entire regions. On the other hand, set against that, was the early conservation movement, a typical example of fundamentalism, static, appealing to a past order and community in reaction to the dynamism of modernity. To people like William Morris, what was important was to preserve the actual old fabric at all costs. The absolute new was set against the absolute old: a harshly confrontational framework for a harshly confrontational age. Both extremes replaced aspects of religion with utopian social visions - in the case of conservation, to the point of idolatry in its presumption that human works could be preserved for all time. But at the same time, their peaceful clash left its traces of life and vigour across our continent.

What we have now is quite different, and resembles the longstanding position in North America, a society 'modern' from the start, where that sharp polarisation never existed. Now, the Modern Movement heritage is integrated into a polycentric setting in which 'historic landmarks' are studded like countless Colonial Williamsburg theme parks in the dynamic, but directionless spread of Clone City, an environment dedicated as a whole to marketing and capitalist growth. MoMo relics, shorn of their dynamic social and spatial context, have been absorbed into the static heritage zones, where the Morris-style insistence on preserving actual old fabric is applied to them as if they were medieval cathedrals. And the meaning of these relics has radically changed, too. They have been stripped of Modernism's radical ideals of social reconstruction, leaving only a meaningless stylistic shell of 'heroic form' that can be commodified and plundered by today's signature-designers in creating image-buildings for cities to compete with each other in the global marketplace. What is valued is not the essence of the Modernist programme - the mass social building, the planning concepts - but marketable individual buildings and designers. For example, in Scotland, the cult of C R Mackintosh is seen as providing a precedent for the meretricious image-making of Enric Miralles's design for the new Scottish parliament building, like a theme-park pavilion in its attempt to 'symbolise Scotland' through 'upturned boats'. In this context, the researches of DOCOMOMO into the heroic age of Modernism have arguably helped feed the mounting capitalis-

tic frenzy. The Modern Movement always presented itself as an internationalist, universalising movement, but it was assumed that what was meant was socialist, not capitalist globalisation.

What escape is there from this seemingly relentless march of international homogeneity? It's too strong and pervasive for any outright fundamentalist opposition to be effective. Equally, traditional critical regionalism provides no way out, as it is just as concerned with images - indeed, you could almost argue that Miralles's boats and leaves, for all their obvious opportunism, are exemplary critical regionalist objects. What I want to do is to point, in the context of this session, to a possibility that the designing of landscape space, as opposed to single object-buildings, could perhaps be a means of regeneration. The High MoMo era would have referred to this kind of landscape overview as 'planning'. But that doesn't mean we're talking about the dirigiste *tabula rasa* plans, universal abstract prescriptions and authoritarian openness of CIAM Modernism, with *Zeilenbau* slabs marching to the horizon, and the state as the executor and guarantor of Progress. Nor do I mean what today is called 'planning': the bureaucratic control mechanism, especially in the heritage field, that reinforces the static subdivisions of Clone City.

What I mean by 'planning' and landscape space is openness as a spatial frame of mind; an insistence on looking outwards beyond the specific and the commodifiable to the built environment overall. I want to suggest that we can use the modern heritage to help build a new critical regionalism in Europe by concentrating not on MoMo architectural style but on the composite legacies left by the different, longer trajectories of modernisation in different places.

In other words, we can make 20th century MoMo space mean something by putting it in the context of earlier modernising spatial concepts: because, as I say, unlike North America, historic Europe is built up of many layers of modern visions. That heritage of modern spaces and landscapes goes, of course, right back to ancient Greece, but that is a general heritage for all of us. Within individual countries, it is most highly developed in places like Scotland and England where social and economic modernisation came early, in the 18th century, in a revolution of rationalised agriculture, rapidly followed by the building of planned settlements and the industrialisation of the urban built environment.

In such countries, the historic built landscape is a landscape of pervasive planned modernity, and any talk of a pre-industrial golden age of 'traditional' life is meaningless. 'Modern landscape' can mean something of the late 18th as well as of the 20th century, and we today in turn can add our own kind

of modernity to that layering. That, at any rate, was the belief of a grouping of late 19th and 20th century critics and planners, stemming from the work of the Edinburgh-based social thinker Patrick Geddes, and inspired especially by the close, symbiotic juxtaposition of Edinburgh's medieval Old Town and the planned classical New Town. I'd like to spend the last few minutes of my talk outlining their ideas. Geddes was provoked by a very similar capitalist crisis of fragmentation to our own. His remedy for this 'Palaeotechnic Age' was 'Neotechnic planning'. By 'planning' he meant not command planning dedicated to materialist Progress, but what he called the creation of 'Centres of Life', which would form part of a constant cyclical process of renewal: the *Arbor Saeculorum* (Tree of the Epochs). As to what this meant in spatial terms, Geddes set out to reconcile the traditional identity of dense urban form and urban culture with the openness and freedom of the modern urban area, for which he coined the name 'conurbation'. The key aim was to keep the market from breaking down the sharpness of that landscape relationship, but instead to intensify it by coordinating the city with the rural hinterland, on the explicit model of the ancient Greek *polis*. Geddes called for 'a rebuilding of analysis into Synthesis, an integration of the narrow window of the individual outlook for the open tower which overlooks college and city'. Within the city itself, while the spirit of place was important, the actual old fabric was secondary: old buildings could readily be demolished for practical or symbolic improvements.

Despite his opposition to state socialism, Geddes's concept of place-specific modernity greatly influenced the mid 20th century era of Modernist grand plans, when a range of Scottish city and regional planners, led by architect Robert Matthew, built their proposals on the 18th-20th century legacy of agricultural improvement and new-town building. They shared Geddes's contempt for the free market as regulator of landscape quality. And they were all highly sensitive to the particular trajectory of modernity in the region concerned. The main contrast was between 'historic' Edinburgh and the East and the more industrial, frankly modern Glasgow and the West. Their contrast became like that of the Edinburgh Old and New Towns writ large.

In the Clyde Valley, the essence of modern planning seemed to be the radical policy of planting new industrial communities in dramatic landscape - epitomised by the 18th-century mill village of New Lanark. So the Clyde Valley Regional Plan of 1946, co-authored by Matthew with Patrick Abercrombie, proposed a vast programme of population 'overspill' from Glasgow slums to new towns in landscape, and a green belt around Glasgow to check periph-

eral sprawl. In the East Coast around Edinburgh, on the other hand, the strategy adopted was to modernise the many historic towns in a respectful way, intensifying existing settlements rather than building new ones. In the work of Scottish government chief planner Robert Grieve, the Geddesian polis-in-hinterland regional planning ethos was also prominent.

Robert Matthew's own personal interventions mirrored this east-west contrast: in the Gorbals slum redevelopment in Glasgow (1958-64), for example, he designed a ruthlessly daylight-aligned pattern of towers, while in the Edinburgh University redevelopment (1960-8) he inserted a tower block group tactfully on one side of a classical square; and in 1970, he instigated an immensely important project to rescue the 18th-century Edinburgh New Town: the New Town Conservation Committee. Matthew made strenuous efforts to keep these initiatives in an international context, through constant collaborations with like minded thinkers - for example, he was a close friend of the Greek polymath architect Dinos Doxiadis, a mid-century equivalent to Geddes who devised an entire science of human settlement, or 'Ekistics', based on a complex theoretical framework of spatial-social patterns, ultimately inspired by the rationalistic planning of the ancient Greek polis.

If Matthew's socialistic age could make use of these Geddesian ideas, how much more relevant are they to us today, facing a new 'Palaeotechnic Age' of global capitalistic chaos! In the relations between people like Matthew and Doxiadis, we witness a kind of international regionalism which can help us to fight the international juggernaut of Clone City. The struggle over landscape, whether in Scotland, Greece or Finland, is just a fragment of the pan-European struggle between identity and savage capitalism. So far, the contribution of the Modernist heritage interest to this struggle, in its emphasis on heroic form, has merely been to fuel a free-trade in empty images, in instant identities dressed up like marketing brands. But it's through the inspiration not of the works of heroic artists like Aalto, Corbusier or Mackintosh, but of the more complex landscape visions of people like Geddes and his disciples that the Modern Movement can help us today build a real critical regionalism, a real identity, in historic Europe today.

NOTES

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KEYWORDS

plannillg; globalisation; Patrick Geddes; urbanism

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